

Section 1: Applicants

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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Infrastructures for Diamond Open Access in the Netherlands
Project duration (in months)	48 months

English public summary

Infrastructures for Diamond Open Access plans to set up a high-quality and flexible national publication infrastructure that can be made available to all university presses, research institutes, and other research organisations that wish to develop and publish their own articles, journals and (text)books. The infrastructure builds upon already existing academic library-led publication infrastructures, the so-called Netherlands University Presses (NUPs), and Openjournals. All of these have demonstrated their dedication to open science principles by using technology based on open-source software, having a community-based governance and adherence to diamond open access models and FAIR data principles.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 95

Dutch public summary

Infrastructures for Diamond Open Access wil een hoogwaardige en flexibele nationale publicatie-infrastructuur opzetten die beschikbaar kan worden gesteld aan alle universitaire uitgeverijen, onderzoeksinstituten en andere academische organisaties die hun eigen artikelen, tijdschriften en (tekst)boeken willen ontwikkelen en publiceren. Het project bouwt voort op al bestaande, door academische bibliotheken geleide uitgevers, de zogenaamde Netherlands University Presses (NUPs) en Openjournals. Al deze infrastructuren hebben hun toewijding aan de principes van open wetenschap aangetoond door gebruik te maken van technologie op basis van open source software, een op gemeenschappen gebaseerd bestuur en door zich te richten op diamond open access en FAIR-data principes.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 100

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

The current landscape of diamond open access publishing in the Netherlands is supported by decentralised, institution-led platforms. While these infrastructures—such as the university libraries' NUPs and Openjournals—have demonstrated their commitment to open science, the lack of integration limits efficiency, scalability, and national coordination. This project aims to develop a unified, future-proof national infrastructure for diamond open access publishing that can be made available to all university presses, research institutes, and other research organisations that wish to develop and publish their own articles, journals and (text)books.

The infrastructure will use open-source software and adhere to community-led standards. It will support the entire publishing workflow, including hosting, archiving, metadata management, and usage reporting. By harmonising the present services, the national infrastructure will reduce operational costs, support editorial independence, and simplify access to high-quality, sustainable publishing tools for institutions across the country.

Aligned with the objectives of this call, the project enhances an existing ecosystem and offers a coherent, scalable solution to strengthen open science throughout the Netherlands by means of shared infrastructure, governance, interoperability, and efficient use of public funds.

Word count SEC31 (max. 200): 179

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

This proposal addresses a key challenge in the open science landscape, namely that institutional diamond open access publishers often operate on limited budgets, making it difficult to scale their operations, demonstrate impact, and gain recognition. Existing infrastructures are fragmented and not sufficiently coordinated to meet the collective needs of these publishers.

By developing a shared national infrastructure for diamond open access publishing, the project increases efficiency, continuity, quality and effectiveness across institutions. It allows publishers to focus on supporting authors and editorial boards, while benefiting from shared tools and services for quality assurance, dissemination, and preservation.

Researchers gain access to a robust, cost-free publishing environment that preserves author rights and offers a credible, community-driven alternative to commercial publishers. Editorial boards benefit from technical and editorial support within a professional network.

The infrastructure also meets the needs of learned societies and research organisations by making diamond open access publishing more accessible and affordable to all researchers in the Netherlands. These needs are not fully met by current systems, which is why this national, collaborative solution is both timely and necessary.

Word count SEC32 (max. 300): 179

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

The Open Science values and principles we adhere to are: Open, Transparent, Collaboration, Collective benefit, and Equity. This project aligns with these values and principles by creating a more open and transparent, collaborative publishing infrastructure which serves the greater good and reduces our dependency on commercial publishers (collective benefit) while ensuring equal opportunities for all to engage with, benefit from, contribute to, and learn from the scientific process (equity).

The infrastructure will use technology based on open-source software and adhere to open community-led standards, diamond open access models and FAIR data principles. The community-based governance structure ensures transparent decision-making with input from the user community.

Societal impact

This project contributes to the removal of barriers around creating, reading, reusing and evaluating scholarly output by offering a cost-effective publishing venue for authors and editorial boards, a standard use of CC-licensing and active dissemination of output, and thus leading to societal impact by making scientific knowledge openly accessible to everyone.

Academic and digital sovereignty

Academic sovereignty and the autonomy regarding sustainable digital information services and infrastructure are under pressure as universities are increasingly dependent on commercial providers. This dependency increases the influence of external (commercial) parties and can lead to the erosion of academic freedoms of universities and researchers. Within the Netherlands there is a growing call for the promotion of services and technologies developed with academic values and the public interest in mind and diversifying the digital portfolio. In this sense, a shared national publishing infrastructure contributes to safeguarding academic and digital sovereignty by offering a complementary alternative to commercial publishers and creating a pluralistic, rich scholarly publishing landscape consisting of multiple inclusive, sustainable and equitable publishing models.

Word count SEC33 (max. 300): 277

3.4 Access policy

Institutional membership will be made available universities affiliated with the Universities of the Netherlands, universities of applied sciences, university medical centres, institutes affiliated to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences or NWO, Rijksmuseums and other research organisations that wish to develop and publish their own articles, journals and books. Membership is based on agreement to international publishing standards (COPE, Plan S, rigorous peer review) to ensure high quality publishing. Yearly fees are set at cost and without profit margin, to cover the infrastructure costs (hosting, domain name registration), technical support, and further development of the infrastructure.

Word count SEC34 (max. 150): 98

3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

Our infrastructure shall actively contribute to the (inter-)national research publication landscape by sharing knowledge with initiatives, such as [Craft-OA's Diamond Discovery Hub](#), OAPEN, [Open Research Europe](#), the [European Quality Standard for Institutional Open Access Publishing \(EQSIP\)](#) developed by DIAMAS and similar national diamond open access publishing infrastructures (such as Tidsskrift.dk from Denmark, Edition from Finland and Scottish Universities Press) that offer national publishing services.

Within the Netherlands we'll align with other national collaborative projects *UKB Publishing Browser*, *DURF - Dutch Repository Federation*, *BROCCOLI - a federated hub for healthy Dutch ORI*, *Platform for Meaningful access WijsNL* and *Next-generation publishing: advancing the PRC model*.

In addition, the OSNL-proposal National Diamond Open Access Books Platform can be seen as a (necessary) extension of existing publication infrastructures. Our project builds on suitable and presently used software and Open Monograph Systems as an option. We'll connect to activities coming forth from the OSNL-proposals *Enabling and Strengthening Institutional Publishing*, and *Scaling small in NL - Implementing a joint metadata management system to enable joint outputs and services in partnership with Open Access Book infrastructure services* by the Netherlands University Presses.

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 184

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

The formation of a shared national publication infrastructure will be done in stages. The work packages indicated below aren't necessarily sequential.

Work package 1: Integration into one shared publication infrastructure

WP 1 integrates the existing infrastructures into one shared national publication infrastructure for Diamond OA publishing. This stage involves the testing and adaptation of publication software to ensure the infrastructure fits the needs of the affiliated organisations, the integration of backfiles into the new infrastructure, usability testing by publishers and editors and phasing out currently existing infrastructures from participants.

The infrastructure will provide an architecture that allows publishers to select those modules that fall within their publishing strategy. A web delivery platform consisting of a front-end and an admin module, brings together publications from multiple sources within a single interface, displays them and enables readers to discover and use them (display, discovery, dissemination).

In implementing the following components, we will be supported by SURF. SURF applies a structured and proven process for developing services, guided by a comprehensive checklist, public values and governance framework. As part of the quality standards - including architecture, procurement, legal, security and privacy by design - compliance and responsible practices are ensured. SURF's expertise provides robust support for the creation of a national Diamond OA service development.

Key activities

- Design and development of web delivery platform
- Installation, testing and configuration of publication software
- Connecting software to services around cataloguing, indexing and archiving
- Migration of files to (new) infrastructure
- Enhancement of metadata of articles and journals
- Phasing out existing publication infrastructures
- Development of documentation and training materials for end users
- Setting up workflows around financial administration
- Setting up organisational governing (legal structure, agreement with software management organisation)
- Setting up workflows, protocols and quality assurance
- Setting up organisation: staff, advisory board, etc.

Work package 2: selection and harmonisation of services

WP2 focuses on establishing a catalogue of shared editorial and production services for (future) member publishers, academic authors and journal editors. Sharing these services increases efficiency, reduces operational costs and allows participatory publishers to easily access professional editorial services without having to individually develop these. WP2 will also allow for experimentation with innovative workflows and embedding digital media resources into publications.

Key Activities

- Analyse the presently used editorial and production services
- Determine the scope (which services to be shared)
- Formulate requirements for shared services
- Formulate agreements with responsible parties
- Develop documentation and training materials
- Develop workflows for experimental publishing

Work package 3: safeguarding infrastructures

WP 3 works towards safeguarding the developed shared national publishing infrastructure and harmonised services by embedding these at the national level. Focus is on governance and a sustainable financial structure. Please also see Section 5.1 Sustainability Plan.

WP 3 will be executed throughout the entire project (2026 - 2029)

Key Activities

- Stakeholder management
- Development of scenarios on governance and financial model
- Agreement between stakeholders on a governance structure and a long term sustainable financial model

Work package 4: Communication

For current users of the existing infrastructures, things are going to change. This can lead to uncertainties and questions. It is therefore important to involve editorial boards and authors in the journey to a national platform at an early stage. To this end, communication materials will be developed that can be used by project participants in all phases of the project when communicating with their users.

It is important that the institutions' identity is and remains guaranteed. To this end, it shall be transparent on the platform which institution has published which publication, by using filters in the catalogue, logos, adding institution-DOI and making an information page about participating partners. In the third phase, a brand strategy will be developed and implemented to promote the shared national infrastructure to various target groups.

WP 4 will be executed throughout the entire project (2026 - 2029)

Key Activities

- Develop a communication strategy
- Develop communication materials
- Design a brand strategy

Word count SEC 41 (max. 750): 743

4.2 Team composition

The project will be executed by UKB, with the Erasmus University Rotterdam as project lead. The project team consists of a dedicated project manager, complemented with representatives from the present Netherlands University Presses (Maastricht University Press, Open Press Tilburg University, Radboud University Press, TUDelft Open Publishing and University of Groningen Press) and Openjournals.

In addition, SURF will provide expertise on publication services and will participate in preparing scenarios for the integration of the existing infrastructures. A steering committee of senior management of the participating organisations monitors the quality, coherence, finances and strategic direction between the different project components.

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 331

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Developments within national and European politics (cuts in higher education), policy requirements around Open Access and publication policies of research funders.	Likelihood: medium, impact: medium to high	Resizing of work packages (f.e. cancelling WP2)
With the current cuts to higher education, it is assumed that staff within university libraries will not be replaced. Project work is mostly carried out in addition to regular duties, making it vulnerable for acquittal.	Likelihood: medium; impact: high	Resizing of work packages
Loss of support of participants. Standardisation may jeopardise the delivery of customisation to authors and create a dependence on other organisations to provide expertise and carry out activities.	Likelihood: low, impact: medium	Continuously check if interests, goals, and expectations are aligned
When not convinced of the underlying value of diamond open access stakeholders might pull back their support, making the investment a heavier burden on other participants.	Likelihood: medium, impact: medium	Continuously check if interests, goals, and expectations are aligned
Infrastructure not becoming an integral part of the research community.	Likelihood: low, impact: high	Strong focus on community engagement

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 183

4.4 Budget

Total Personnel requested: €1.448.576,30

Total Material/IT requested: €51.420,00

Total budget requested: €1.499.996,30

4.5 Budget justification

A significant portion of the requested budget is allocated to personnel costs, which are essential for the successful execution and long-term sustainability of this national infrastructure project. Costs are distributed across both national coordinating bodies (UKB and SURF) and the directly involved stakeholders, such as the NUPs and Openjournals.

Currently the NUPs and Openjournals operate as decentralised systems, and are expected to transition to a shared, centralised infrastructure as a result of this project. To achieve this, several specialised IT-roles are required. Development staff will be responsible for the installation and configuration of open-source publication platforms, as well as the development of a web delivery platform for display and discovery. Besides, developers will work on the integration of middleware services that connect to shared functionalities like metadata management, archiving, and indexing. Also needed is support of the migration process, which includes the careful and reliable transfer of large volumes of existing publication data from decentralised systems to the new infrastructure.

Beyond technical implementation, project team members will be tasked with ensuring quality assurance, supporting users and governance and policy development. This is essential to ensure the infrastructure functions as a coherent, community-driven system with shared ownership and long-term reliability.

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): 199

4.6 Impact plan

This project will strengthen the scientific, societal, and institutional impact of scholarly publishing by creating a national infrastructure for diamond open access publishing. By supporting open, transparent, and collaborative academic communication, it offers a more inclusive, fair and reliable, community-led alternative to commercial publishing models, which often restrict access, raise costs, and undermine academic autonomy.

The shared infrastructure will facilitate open access publication of journals, articles, and books, removing financial and copyright barriers for researchers, professionals and readers worldwide. It ensures long-term accessibility of research outputs and supports more diverse content, including publications in national languages and on locally relevant topics—creating bibliodiversity by publishing outputs often ignored by commercial publishers.

To fully reach its potential, the project will engage closely with participating partners and users, offering a professional and flexible workflow that adapts to developments in scholarly publishing, supported by a reliable and user-friendly interface.

By centralising core functions and reducing duplication, the infrastructure enables more efficient use of public funds. It enhances the quality and reach of open access publishing and contributes to a fair, cost-effective, and sustainable publication landscape.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 181

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

This proposal is submitted on behalf of **all** universities and is unanimously endorsed by **all** **rectors**. It is seen as important for all Dutch knowledge institutions, fully in line with previously established national ambitions. In addition, the proposal is crucial as part of a shared national infrastructure to make Open Science widely and quickly applicable.

To ensure long-term sustainability, the project focuses on maintaining three key outcomes: (1) a robust, shared national infrastructure for diamond open access publishing; (2) integrated services that support dissemination, preservation, and transparency; and (3) strong engagement and participation from the academic community. This requires a multifaceted approach, focused on governance, technology, resources (staff and funding) and community engagement, as indicated by the Sustainability Wheel on the left (Gemmill Arp, 2018).

During the first two years of the project we'll focus on a small set of strongly committed stakeholders and seek agreement on core values and alignment around a core purpose. In the fourth year the transition from project to a sustainable program will take place, moving control from founding stakeholders and sponsors to multiple stakeholders representative of the growing community. These tasks will be taken up in WP3. We'll aim to reach consolidation with a range of predictable

elements (such as revenue streams, business apparatus, and technology), leaving flexibility to adapt to developments within scholarly publishing.

Technology

We'll embed ourselves in the scholarly communication strategy by developing a strong network of relationships and partnerships with other projects and organisations, such as mentioned in 3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem. The placement of the development and maintenance of the infrastructure at a central public organisation will contribute to creating a fixed position in the Dutch research landscape.

Resources

Dedicated staff, such as product manager, application developers and communications specialist, will be fundamental in order to maintain quality. Investments will have to be made in building expertise in technology, metadata and leadership. Financial resources must be available for maintenance and continued development of services and tools.

Community Engagement

Community engagement is part of WP4 and includes communication and outreach efforts to the community itself as well as the wider world of decision makers, potential users, and funding agencies.

Governance

As part of WP3 we'll design a governance model for the longer term. In order to increase commitment governance will be based on shared ownership with a representative of all member organisations in the management board, so that all participants have an equal voice in decision-making.

Word count SEC51 (max. 450): 422

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

The technical publication infrastructure is built upon proven open source publication software. This software manages the entire researcher-to-reader workflow, including submission, peer review, and production for both journals and books, while still staying flexible and allowing adaptable functionalities. The selected software will be developed and maintained by a community-governed organisation committed to open science, with a strong track record of transparency, stability and adaptability.

The publication platform will be connected to various open-source service providers using middleware. This ensures interoperability and flexibility in offering shared services such as metadata management, indexing, archiving, and usage reporting.

Intended audience for our software are editorial boards, Netherlands University Presses and Openjournals, other academic organisations wishing to publish with a diamond open access model and academic authors of articles and books. On the other hand, the software will also be used by readers, both academic and professionals as within the broader general public.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

All available open source publication software rely on continuous feedback and consultation from their community to grow and enhance their software, for example by providing a requests channel, involving participants in user testing and organising hackathon-like sprints. Changes in functionality by organisations developing open source publication software is communicated amongst others by publishing guides with descriptions of changes and steps for planning and completing migrations or by using the releases tab in Github.

Versioning on the local level will be done by a designated software developer, either on the university or national level and communicated through our website and by recording changes in a file or set of files over time allowing for the identification of specific versions of the software.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

All technical components, documentation, and configurations developed during the project will be made openly available to the open-source community, accompanied by globally unique, persistent, and resolvable identifiers to each release and a CC BY license ensuring transparency, and allowing others—nationally or internationally—to benefit from or build upon the infrastructure.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

Functionalities developed by our own organisation, will be published in a software repository accompanied by a citation file.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

All open source software available provide extensive user documentation on their website, often supplemented by FAQs, a user forum, training webinars and user conferences. Our project team will develop user documentation for authors, editors, and participating institutions, and communicate updates regularly through newsletters and the infrastructure's website. User days will be organised to gather feedback and enhance the user experience.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

On our website we'll provide transparent information on the governance structure, organisation and funders of our publication infrastructure.

7. How will your software be tested?

Organisations providing open source publication software run tests against its software to catch bugs in code before they are released. On local level testing will also be an integral part of developing and maintaining our publication infrastructure and will be done in close collaboration with our (future) users. A standardised test protocol will be developed as part of the application management plan to ensure the stability, compatibility, and performance of the middleware across infrastructure updates and service integrations. This protocol will be used to validate new releases, onboard new users, and maintain interoperability with connected open-source services.

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8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

The selected publication software provider guarantees routinely checks of licenses of libraries and dependencies and works with them accordingly.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

The selected publication software provider will provide a clear directory structure, including a README file for instructions, a LICENSE file to specify usage rights, and a CONTRIBUTING guide to help others get involved. The provider uses a package manager relevant to their language and includes metadata like version, dependencies, and author information. Releases are tagged in version control and published to a public registry.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

We'll provide extensive user guides for editorial boards, authors and participating organisations on the website of our platform. Also, technical assistance will be provided as part of the standard service.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

Daily maintenance, such as patching, bug fixing, dependency updates, and security checks will be carried out by a dedicated software developer.

In the final phase of the project, a sustainable application management plan will be implemented. While the software and services are open source, a coordinated plan remains essential to ensure reliable performance, version control, and security across connected components. This plan will support integration with new releases, centralise responsibility for coordination, and ensure that systems remain aligned as the infrastructure evolves.

To support future growth, the application management plan will include onboarding procedures for new users and institutions. This ensures technical scalability and readiness for integration, allowing research organisations, publishers, or editorial boards to connect efficiently to the infrastructure as their needs evolve.

The infrastructure will be embedded in a supported academic ecosystem on the national level, making it resilient and durable.

Section 6: References

Laurie Gemmill and Megan Forbes, "It Takes a Village: Open Source Software Sustainability. A Guidebook for Programs Serving Cultural and Scientific Heritage" (Lyrisis, February 2018), <https://itav.lyrisis.org/guidebook>.

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.